

VIRTUAL SENSING FOR ELECTRIC MOTOR AND INVERTER CONTROL

EM-TECH

Politecnico di Torino

Temperature estimation methodology can be applied to alternative electric machines

Practical and numerical experience in temperature estimation for critical systems

CHALLENGES & SOLUTION:

The challenge was to develop a reliable and robust virtual temperature sensor to estimate the temperature of the permanent magnets in a permanent-magnet synchronous machine. The outcome takes the form of a hybrid solution consisting of a physics-based solution, coupled with a neural network representing the nonlinear component. A Hammerstein model structure is employed, with a lumped-parameter thermal network representing the thermal behavior of the system, with input non-linearities being appropriately treated with a sigmoid neural network. A data-driven approach is taken to correctly identify the model parameters, starting from numerical and experimental test data sets. In addition, the outcome from this work includes a Precise Flux Observer which is designed and implemented as an alternative solution, following a similar development path as the previous solution. Experimental data obtained by Elaphe is exploited to tune this model. The estimation of the permanent magnet temperature enables for a safer operation of the electric machine during service, while exploiting its maximum capability.

IMPACT & NEXT STEPS:

Virtual temperature sensing enables for more effective utilization of electric machines, operating them close to their thermal limits while maintaining performance. The solutions developed have the potential to be adapted to meet multiple product ranges offered by a manufacturer.

Figure 1: Permanent magnet temperature estimation performed on embedded hardware enables for higher machine utilization.

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